

GUANYLALKYLUREAS AND THEIR METALLIC COMPLEXES. PART V. PALLADIUM COMPLEXES*

BY R. L. DUTTA, BIMANESH SUR AND NIHAR RANJAN SENGUPTA

Complex compounds of palladium (II) with guanylalkylureas have been prepared and their properties studied. The complex palladium *bis*-guanylalkylurea bases and their salts are all pale cream in colour. The equivalent conductance measurements indicate the bivalent nature of the complex cation. The compounds are all diamagnetic, suggesting a planar structure with d_{sp^2} hybrid bonds.

The cream-coloured palladium *bis*-guanylalkylurea thiocyanates undergo rearrangement in presence of dilute acid to form ruby-red palladium *bis*-guanylalkylurea-palladothiocyanate.

Palladium(II) complexes of unsubstituted guanylurea and of phenylguanylurea have been studied by Rây and Bandopadhyay (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 865). A series of guanylalkylureas have recently been prepared, and comprehensive studies of the copper and nickel complexes of these ligands recorded in the earlier parts of this series (Dutta and Rây, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 499, 567, 576). The present work was undertaken with a view to making a comparative study of the behaviour of nickel(II) and palladium(II). It deals with the preparation and properties of the palladium (II) complexes of guanylmethyl-, -ethyl-, -butylⁿ-, -butylⁱ-, -amylⁱ- and -hexylⁿureas.

The compounds can be represented as :

- I. $[\text{Pd}(\text{Gau})_2]$ or $[\text{Pd}(\text{Gau})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where $\text{GauH} =$ a molecule of guanylalkylurea.
- II. $[\text{Pd}(\text{GauH})_2] \cdot X_{2 \cdot x}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where $X = \text{Cl}, \frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4, \text{NO}_3, \text{SCN}$, etc.
- III. $[\text{Pd}(\text{GauH})_2] [\text{Pd}(\text{SCN})_4]$

The complex palladium (II)-*bis*-guanylalkylurea sulphates have been prepared as sparingly soluble products by the addition of a solution of sodium chloropalladite to that of the guanylalkylurea sulphate in neutral or faintly ammoniacal medium.

The complex chlorides were prepared either by the action of barium chloride on the complex sulphate or by neutralising the complex base with hydrochloric acid. The solubility of the chloride salts in water decreases with increase in the chain length of the substituent at the urea end of the molecule, whereas that in alcohol increases. Several salts of the complex bases, namely, iodide, nitrate and thiocyanate, were obtained as silky, cream-coloured crystalline precipitates by double decomposition between the complex chloride and the appropriate alkali metal salt in aqueous $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ in aqueous alcoholic solution. The complex palladium guanylethylurea bases and those of the higher guanylureas were prepared as water-insoluble products by digesting a solution of sodium chloropalladite and the guanylalkylurea concerned in presence of sodium hydroxide. It has not been possible, however, to isolate the complex palladium guanylmethylurea base due to its extreme solubility in water. The complex bases in the solid state conform to the composition of anhydro-bases or to hemi-hydrates. These liberate ammonia from ammonium salts and react alkaline to litmus.

Complex palladium-*bis*-guanylalkylurea thiocyanates on treatment with dilute acid solution deposited a ruby-red insoluble mass, characterised as the palladium-*bis*-guanylalkylurea palladothiocyanate.

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In this respect, the complex palladium-guanyurea thiocyanates resemble their biguanide analogues (Rây and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 19).

The complexes are all stable in boiling water or alcohol. The equivalent conductances of the chloride salts of the palladium guanylmethylurea and of palladium guanylethylurea in water are in fair agreement with those of bi-univalent electrolytes. The compounds are all diamagnetic, indicating a planar structure characteristic of penetration complexes of palladium with dsp^2 bonds. These compounds show a close similarity to the corresponding nickel complexes in respect of composition, properties and also magnetic characteristics. Like nickel, palladium (II) also does not form any *mono-guanylmethylurea* complex. Nickel (II) and palladium (II) thus present a marked difference from copper (II), so far as their behaviour towards biguanides and guanyureas is concerned.

EXPERIMENTAL

Complex Compounds of Palladium with Guanylmethylurea

Palladium-bis-guanylmethylurea Sulphate.—An aqueous solution of sodium chloropalladite (PdCl_2 , 0.5 g.) was added to that of guanylmethylurea sulphate (1.3 g.) (total volume 80 c.c.) and cooled in an ice bath. The complex palladium sulphate separating as a fine, silky, pale cream, crystalline mass was filtered, washed with water and little ethanol, and dried in air. {Found: Pd, 23.01; SO_4 , 20.65; N, 23.65; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 7.52. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 22.75; SO_4 , 20.47; N, 28.88; H_2O , 7.67%}. $x_g = -0.15 \times 10^{-6}$.

Chloride.—Complex palladium sulphate (2 g.), obtained as above, was suspended in water (30 c.c.) and digested on a water bath with barium chloride (1 g. in 30 c.c.) solution for about an hour. The mixture was then filtered, the filtrate concentrated (25 c.c.) on the water bath and left in the frigidare overnight. The pale cream-coloured crystals separating were filtered, washed first with cold water, then with ethanol, and finally dried in air. {Found: Pd, 24.24; Cl, 16.23; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 8.13. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 24.03; Cl, 16.0; H_2O , 8.10%}.

The *nitrate* was obtained as a precipitate by the interaction of the complex palladium chloride with potassium nitrate in aqueous solution. {Found: Pd, 21.20; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 8.35. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 21.09; H_2O , 8.89%}.

The *iodide*, obtained by the action of KI on the complex chloride, is insoluble in water but readily soluble in ethanol. {Found: Pd, 17.20; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 5.92. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \text{I}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 17.01; H_2O , 5.74%}.

The *thiocyanate*, obtained by the action of KSCN on the complex chloride, was washed with ice-cold water. It is readily soluble in water and in ethanol. {Found: Pd, 22.70; SCN, 24.35; H_2O , 3.96. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] (\text{SCN})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 22.65; SCN, 24.62; H_2O , 3.82%}.

Palladium-bis-guanylmethylurea Palladothiocyanate.—The complex palladium thiocyanate (0.5 g.), obtained as above, was taken in water (40 c.c.), treated with a few drops of HCl (3 N) and digested on a water bath for about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours when ruby-red, silky crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and then dried in air. The same compound was also obtained by the interaction of palladium-bis-guanylmethylurea chloride and potassium palladothiocyanate. {Found: Pd, 31.69; SCN, 34.88. $[\text{Pd} (\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] [\text{Pd} (\text{SCN})_2]$ requires Pd, 31.56; SCN, 34.31%}.

Complex Compounds of Palladium with Guanylethylurea

Palladium bis-Guanylethylurea.—A mixture of sodium chloropalladite (1 M) and guanylethylurea sulphate (1.5 M) was made alkaline with NaOH. A clear solution was obtained, which immediately afterwards deposited a very fine, silky crystalline precipitate. This was filtered. It was washed with water and ethanol, and then dried over KOH. {Found: Pd, 29.02; N, 30.35. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires Pd, 29.23; N, 30.69%}.

The following compounds were obtained as described in the case of guanylmethylurea.

Sulphate: {Found: Pd, 20.47; SO_4 , 18.26; N, 21.46; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 10.85. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 20.63; SO_4 , 18.56; N, 21.66; H_2O , 10.44%}. $\chi_r = -0.12 \times 10^{-8}$.

Nitrate: {Found: Pd, 20.98; H_2O , 1.76. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 0.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 21.34; H_2O , 1.80%}.

Chloride: {Found: Pd, 22.25; Cl, 14.78; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 9.72. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 22.09; Cl, 14.70; H_2O , 9.3%}.

Iodide: {Pd 16.43; H_2O , 5.48. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]\text{I}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 16.23; H_2O , 5.48%}.

Thiocyanate: {Found: Pd, 21.09; SCN, 23.54. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2](\text{SCN})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 21.29; SCN, 23.15%}.

Palladium-bis-guanylethylurea Palladothiocyanate: {Found: Pd, 30.18; SCN, 33.05. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2][\text{Pd}(\text{SCN})_4]$ requires Pd, 30.22; SCN, 32.86%}.

Complex Compounds of Palladium with Guanylbutylurea

Palladium-bis-guanylbutylurea.—A mixture of sodium chloropalladite (1 M) and guanylbutylurea (1.5 M) was made alkaline with NaOH and digested on a water bath for half hour. The precipitated complex base was filtered, washed with water, dissolved in hot ethanol, and reprecipitated with water in the cold. The crystalline precipitate was collected on the filter and dried over KOH. It is slightly soluble in cold ethanol but readily so in the hot. {Found: Pd, 25.01; N, 25.86; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 2.42. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 24.89; N, 26.04; H_2O , 2.09%}.

Chloride.—The complex base, suspended in ethanol in the cold, was neutralised with HCl (dil), resulting in a clear, pale yellow solution. This was then concentrated on a water bath to a small bulk, cooled in ice, and the complex chloride precipitated with the addition of cold water. {Found: Pd, 20.43; Cl, 13.23; H_2O (at 110°), 7.04. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 20.60; Cl, 13.44; H_2O , 6.81%}.

Sulphate: {Found: Pd, 18.94; H_2O (by loss at 110°), 6.18. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 19.22; H_2O , 6.48%}. $\chi_r = -0.09 \times 10^{-8}$.

Palladium-bis-guanylbutylurea was prepared as for the corresponding base of guanylbutylurea. {Found: Pd, 25.16; N, 26.25. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires Pd, 25.34; N, 26.60%}.

Palladium-bis-guanylamylurea: {Found: Pd, 23.58; N, 24.36. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2]$ requires Pd, 23.76; N, 24.94%}. $\chi_r = -0.12 \times 10^{-8}$.

Palladium-bis-guanylohexylurea: {Found: Pd, 21.82; N, 22.89; H_2O , 1.81. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2] \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Pd, 22.04; N, 23.14; H_2O , 1.86%}.

Equivalent Conductance

Measurements of conductance at different dilutions were carried out at 32°. The equivalent conductance at infinite dilution was then calculated with the help of Walden's formula :

$$\Lambda_{\infty} = \Lambda_v (1 + 0.6292 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}}), \text{ where } n_1 \text{ and } n_2 \text{ are the valencies of the ions.}$$

TABLE I

A. Palladium- <i>bis</i> -guanylmethylurea chloride [Pd(C ₂ H ₅ N ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O.				
Dilution (in litres)	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v	72.7	77.2	84.5	83.6
Λ_{∞}	81.6	83.9	89.7	87.2
Λ_{∞} (mean)	85.6. Mol. conduc. = 171.2.			
B. Palladium <i>bis</i> -guanylethylurea chloride [Pd(C ₄ H ₁₀ H ₄ O) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O.				
Dilution (in litres)	64	128	256	1024
Λ_v	86.3	95.4	109.0	118.2
Λ_{∞}	101.3	107.0	118.3	123.2
Λ_{∞} (mean)	112.4. Mol. conduc. = 224.8.			

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE
CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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